

1 **Prdm1 activates BRCA1-type damage signaling and induces a pre-transformation cell cycle**
2 **phenotype.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 PRDM1 expression in human cells resulted in a mixed proliferative phenotype and induced apparent DNA
8 damage or activation of the endogenous repair pathways. Rad9a activation was concomitant with CDKN
9 induction together with CDK6 repression and CDK19 induction, and silencing of Rad23a and Rad23b.
10 BRCA1 damage signaling proceeded through FANCD2/FANCI. Activation of the endogenous imprinting
11 system was prominent, with induction of DZIP3, multiple ZMYM factors, BRWD1 and BAZ2A. PRDM1
12 influenced cell biology and the immune system; activation blocked multiple nuclear transport receptors,
13 silenced innate immune signaling through NLRP2 and AIM2 but activated Z-DNA sensor Zbp1 and the
14 mitochondrial antiviral sensor MAVS. We describe FCMR silencing as a component of the transformation
15 signature. Mismatch repair was mostly unaffected, and p53 was not activated, but Rb1 was. PRDM1
16 exerted oncogenic potential through activation of SS18 and SMARCA1, evidenced by expression of
17 homeobox factors (TCF19, Hhex, Fjx1, Hoxb7, and oncogenes of the ETS, AP-1, and Ras/Raf family.

18 Citations

19 1. Küçük, C., Iqbal, J., Hu, X., Gaulard, P., De Leval, L., Srivastava, G., Au, W.Y., McKeithan, T.W.
20 and Chan, W.C., 2011. PRDM1 is a tumor suppressor gene in natural killer cell malignancies. Proceedings
21 of the National Academy of Sciences, 108(50), pp.20119-20124.
22
23
24
25
26
27
28